

MODELLING OF UNIAXIAL CREEP IN CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES

M. Steen and J. L. Vallés
Institute for Advanced Materials
Joint Research Centre - C. E. C.
P. O. Box 2, NL-1755 ZG Petten, The Netherlands

ABSTRACT

A microstructurally-informed model is developed to describe the uniaxial creep behaviour of a bidirectionally reinforced composite consisting of alumina fibres embedded in a silicon carbide matrix. The model takes into account the creep of fibres and matrix, matrix cracking and the axial stress distributions within the composite. The latter are determined from a modified shear lag analysis which includes the Poisson effect and uses a critical interfacial shear stress as criterion for debonding. This micromechanical model allows the characterisation of the primary and secondary creep stages.

Keywords: ceramic matrix composite, creep, modelling, shear lag analysis

1. INTRODUCTION

Ceramic matrix composites are a novel class of materials that can exhibit considerable increases in toughness and damage tolerance over monolithic ceramics, thereby offering improved potential for use in load-bearing applications. Moreover toughening by continuous fibres is a priori not limited to the low temperature range and therefore continuous fibre reinforced ceramic matrix composites (CFRCMCs) are nowadays actively studied for high temperature structural applications. In view of the multitude of possible fibre and matrix combinations, and the different reinforcement architectures, it is elusive to try to characterise the mechanical behaviour of CFRCMCs experimentally by an exhaustive coverage of the different materials and conditions. Instead, an approach is warranted which is based on the knowledge of the relevant parameters governing the mechanical behaviour and the construction of a model incorporating these parameters. In recent years, substantial progress has been made in the study of deformation and damage in unidirectionally reinforced CFRCMCs under time-independent loading conditions. In particular, the crucial role played by the interface has been acknowledged and different types of mechanical behaviour have been classified in terms of the interfacial parameters and the statistical distribution of in-situ fibre strength [1]. In future anticipated service conditions, however, CFRCMCs will be reinforced in more than one direction, and will be subjected to long term time-dependent loading at high temperatures. A very limited amount of experimental work has been performed in this area, while adequate models describing the mechanical behaviour under these loading conditions are completely lacking. The aim of this paper is to present a model describing the creep behaviour of uniaxially loaded CFRCMCs.

2. MATERIAL AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The material used in this study is a bidirectionally reinforced ceramic matrix composite consisting of plain weave alumina fibre bundles incorporated in a silicon carbide matrix deposited by chemical vapour infiltration (CVI). The composite has a nominal fibre volume fraction of 45% and is produced by Société Européenne de Propulsion, Bordeaux, France. According to the manufacturer, the open porosity lies in the range 10 to 15%, corresponding to a matrix volume fraction of 40 to 45%. Prior to infiltration to form the SiC matrix, the woven Al₂O₃ fibre bundles are stacked and a thin carbon coating is deposited, also by CVI. After infiltration the composite is not provided with an external protective layer against oxidation. In order to study the intrinsic material behaviour at high temperatures, i.e. without the effect of the environment, the mechanical tests are carried out under a vacuum of 10⁻⁴ Pa. Testing is performed in the uniaxial tensile mode on an electromechanical testing machine.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1. Tensile tests

To establish the baseline material data, uniaxial tensile tests to rupture are performed at room temperature and in the temperature range from 950 to 1100 °C on a number of batches of the composite. The tensile curves show a linear elastic region which ends when matrix cracking starts. At higher stresses and strains matrix cracking causes a stress redistribution between the longitudinal fibres and the matrix. This off-loading continues up to saturation of matrix cracking, whereafter the load applied to the composite is taken up entirely by the longitudinal fibre bundles. Failure occurs when the longitudinal fibre bundles are not capable of withstanding further loading. The temperature dependence of the tensile properties is masked by the scatter occurring within a given batch and between batches. This scatter is caused by variations in fibre orientation with respect to the loading axis, by variations of the longitudinal fibre volume fraction, and by variations in porosity level.

3.2. Creep tests

The uniaxial creep tests at applied stresses higher than first matrix cracking stress are performed at the same temperatures as the tensile tests. Creep failure strains are considerably higher than in the tensile tests and can reach values up to 5.6%. At all temperatures the creep curves exhibit primary and tertiary, or primary, secondary and tertiary creep stages at low and high stresses respectively. The primary stage is controlled by the stress redistribution corresponding to off-loading from the matrix to the fibres after matrix cracking has started. At high applied creep stresses, matrix cracking has saturated during loading and the secondary stage reflects the fact that the stresses have fully redistributed between the two constituents of the composite. During this stage the profiles of the axial stresses in the matrix blocks and in the fibres remain constant, resulting in a stationary creep behaviour of the (fibre + matrix) blocks and of the portions of fibre bridging the matrix cracks. In view of the low homologous testing temperatures for the matrix, it is to be expected that creep deformation in this region is controlled by the fibres. The stationary stage extends up to the point where the longitudinal fibres linking the matrix blocks start to fail. The unbroken fibres experience then a load increase and start to creep faster, and the composite enters the tertiary creep stage. The association of the onset of tertiary creep with fibre failure is substantiated by the fact that the fibres themselves do not exhibit any tertiary creep and fail in the secondary stage [2].

The different creep stages are clearly observed in Figure 1 which is a semi-log plot of the instantaneous creep rate versus the accumulated strain. In such a plot, the secondary stage coincides with the region where the logarithm of the creep rate increases linearly with creep strain. The increase is caused by the fact that at constant applied creep load, the true stress on the load-bearing cross section increases. Such a behaviour is observed at high applied stresses where saturation of matrix cracking is achieved during loading up to the creep stress. At low stresses, corresponding to applied stresses which have not resulted in saturation of matrix cracking, the secondary stage is not apparent. Instead, a minimum occurs in the curve, which is a consequence of the competing mechanisms of off-loading from the cracking matrix to the

fibres and the increase in the number of cracks with increasing deformation. As creep deformation accumulates, the rate of matrix cracking decreases. This slows down the creep acceleration and is reflected in the portion of the graph where the curve increases but its slope decreases. As at high stresses, a stationary stage can then occur when saturation of matrix cracking is reached. However, the stationary state is not attained since tertiary creep, triggered by fibre failure, initiates earlier.

Figure 2 shows a Norton plot of the minimum creep rate versus stress applied to the composite. Also shown in the same graph are the results obtained from creep tests on single fibres under argon atmosphere [2]. The best fit to the composite data at high stresses, determined on one batch but also valid for other batches, has a similar slope to that of the fibre data, confirming that the creep behaviour of the composite is controlled by creep of the fibres. However, the fibre data are displaced to higher stress levels. This is because for the composite the nominal stresses have to be corrected for the area fraction of longitudinal fibres in the cross section. In the lower stress range where a minimum instead of a stationary creep rate is observed for the composite, the slope of the best fit is clearly higher than at high stresses. This is a manifestation of the a-physical nature of the minimum creep rate which occurs as a result from the competition between two mechanisms. In the low stress range the creep of the composite is still controlled by the creep of the fibres, but its exact stress dependence is masked by the stress redistribution which is occurring continuously during creep. The above observations are corroborated by the values of the apparent activation energy which are much higher than literature values for creep of CVD SiC [3] and of a SiC-SiC composite [4], and are comparable to that of the fibres tested in inert environment [2].

Figure 1. Creep curves for high and low stress at 1100 °C

The tertiary creep behaviour of the composite is also qualitatively different at high and low stresses. Indeed, as shown in Figure 1, the tertiary creep stage is much more extended and the accumulation of creep strain in the tertiary stage is much higher at low stresses. As explained earlier, the tertiary stage commences when longitudinal fibres start to fail. At high stresses, the

Figure 2. Semi-log plot of instantaneous creep rate versus strain for creep tests at 190 MPa and 100 MPa at 1100 °C

Figure 3. Log plot of minimum creep rate versus applied stress for the composite compared to data from single fibre tests

redistributed load on the fibres is high and consequently the probability of fibre failure is also high. Moreover, once fibres start to fail, a proportionately larger amount of load has to be transferred to the remaining unbroken fibres than at lower stresses. As a result, the remaining fibres break at a higher rate, thus reducing both the extent of the tertiary creep stage as well as the contribution of fibre creep and pullout to the accumulation of deformation during this stage.

4. CREEP MODEL

With the aim of rationalising the experimental data, and providing a basis on which extrapolations can be made, a model for the primary and secondary creep stages in a CFRCMC has been developed. As a starting point, the model proposed by Goto and McLean [5] to study the creep of unidirectionally reinforced metallic matrix composites has been extended to also include creep of the fibres. The stress redistribution causing primary creep is described through an internal variable formalism. The results show that it is possible to describe the primary and secondary stages on the basis of the results from tensile tests and from a short term creep test. However, a more realistic model requires taking the occurrence of matrix cracking into account when incorporating the redistribution of stresses between the matrix and the longitudinal fibre bundles. To accomplish this, the stress profiles in a "microcomposite" consisting of a single fibre surrounded by a mantle of matrix, are calculated using a modified shear lag model that accounts for the existence of different regimes along the interface between the matrix and fibre, viz. unaffected contact, relative slip, and complete detachment [6]. As opposed to similar models, radial compression of the interface is not a prerequisite. The model takes the Poisson effect into account and uses a critical shear stress criterion for interfacial debonding. The input parameters are listed in Table 1. Their values are either taken from literature, or are derived from the experimental data on first and saturated matrix cracking stress versus temperature and ultimate composite stress. The values of the axial thermal expansion coefficient and elastic modulus of the fibres determined in this way are smaller than published values obtained from single fibre tests. In the case of both properties, part of the difference is caused by the fact that here the in-situ fibre properties have to be considered instead, which may differ significantly from pure fibre properties [e.g. 7]. A second reason lies in the fact that the fibres are incorporated in the composite in the form of woven bundles, and consequently they are bent. The resulting increased compliance causes a decrease in the elastic modulus. In the case of the axial thermal expansion coefficient the concomitant decrease is added to by the restraining effect of the surrounding matrix. The value determined for the friction coefficient agrees nicely with published values for ceramic matrix composites where the interface is subjected to radial tension and interfacial friction is known to arise from asperity contact along the surface roughness of the fibre or fibre coating [8]. As an additional outcome of the model, values for other material properties can be derived. These are listed in Table 2. The values obtained for the volume fractions of the different constituents are perfectly reasonable, as well as the derived strength values for the SiC matrix. For the derived fibre properties, again in-situ values are obtained.

An example of the axial stress profiles for the fibre and matrix, as well as the shear stress profile within a matrix block obtained from the shear lag analysis are shown in Figure 4. For the experimental conditions considered two regions appear within the matrix block: unaffected contact and relative slip between fibre and matrix. The axial stress profiles for matrix and fibre obtained from the shear lag analysis are used as input to the earlier creep model, which is slightly modified to allow for creep within a matrix block (corresponding to the three above mentioned zones) and for creep of the fibres bridging the matrix cracks and linking the different blocks. Fitting the stress exponents of fibre and matrix to a high stress reference creep curve, the result of which is shown in Figure 5, gives optimum values of 4 and 1 respectively. The stress exponent for the fibres agrees very well with published fibre creep data [2], while the matrix stress exponent corresponds to that for diffusional creep. In view of the low homologous temperature for SiC and the experimentally covered stress range, diffusion creep is quite probably the dominating creep mechanism for the matrix. The physically meaningful values for the stress exponents allow a confident extrapolation to lower stresses. As an example of such an extrapolation at the highest testing temperature of 1100 °C the predicted minimum creep rates at lower stresses are compared to the experimental ones in figure 6. As it can be

observed, acceptable agreement is obtained for stress levels above the first matrix cracking stress.

Table 1: Input parameters to the modified shear lag model

parameter	determined from
elastic modulus of matrix	literature + tensile tests
Poisson ratio of matrix	literature
Poisson ratio of fibre	literature
axial thermal expansion coefficient of matrix	literature
transverse thermal expansion coefficient of fibre	literature
fibre radius	micrographs
half matrix block length	experiment
matrix mantle radius	experimental in-situ fibre failure strength and volume fractions
elastic modulus of fibre	tensile tests
axial thermal expansion coefficient of fibre	temperature dependence of first matrix cracking stress
friction coefficient	experimental saturated matrix crack spacing as a function of temperature
normal strength of the interface	
temperature difference from composite manufacturing temperature	

Table 2: values of derived properties

property	value
fibre volume fraction	0.53
matrix volume fraction	0.32
porosity	0.15
characteristic in-situ fibre strength	363 MPa
maximum fibre stress at failure	261 MPa
matrix tensile strength (for first matrix cracking)	208 MPa
matrix tensile strength at saturation (corresponding to small gauge length)	340 MPa
frictional shear stress along the interface	2.6 MPa

5. CONCLUSIONS

The mechanisms of primary, secondary and tertiary creep in a bidirectionally continuous fibre reinforced ceramic matrix composite have been studied. Primary creep is caused by the stress redistribution between matrix and longitudinal fibres occurring after loading due to the difference in elastic properties. The stationary creep of the composite is governed by creep of the fibres. The double power law dependence of the minimum creep rate on the applied stress originates from the transient process of matrix cracking resulting in a non-stationary stress redistribution between matrix and fibres. Tertiary creep is caused by the stress redistribution occurring when fibres start to fail. This increases the creep rate of the still unbroken fibres and also results in a pullout contribution to creep. The difference in the extent of the tertiary creep stage and in the level of the rupture strains for high and low stresses is due to the different way in which the statistical distribution of the in-situ fibre strength affects the stress redistribution between failed and unfailed fibres.

A creep model has been proposed to describe the primary and secondary creep of the composite. The axial stress profiles in the fibre and the matrix mantle of the microcomposite, serving as representative volume element of the composite, are an input to the model. These stress profiles are obtained from a modified shear lag analysis which accounts for the possible existence of three regions within a matrix block after matrix cracking has occurred. The model

Figure 4. Axial and interfacial shear stress profiles within half a matrix block

Figure 5. Comparison of experimental and fitted creep curve at 1100 °C and 190 MPa

Figure 6. Comparison of extrapolated minimum creep rates at 1100 °C with experimental data

provides also reasonable values for other properties which are hardly accessible by experimentation. The stress exponents obtained for stationary creep of fibre and matrix agree well with literature values. The possibility of using the model for extrapolation purposes is under study, as well as the incorporation of tertiary creep and the bidirectional nature of the reinforcement.

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**CERAMIC MATRIX
COMPOSITES:
FRACTURE
AND DAMAGE**
